

VERITY

SCENARIO-BUILDING TRAINING FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF RECOMMENDATIONS

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SCENARIO-BUILDING TRAINING FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF RECOMMENDATIONS

Building on the Scenario-Building Workshop held on 27 March 2025, led by Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI) with support from other VERITY partners, the project developed a Scenario-Building Training to help stakeholders put the [VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science](#) into practice. The training offers a step-by-step methodological tool for exploring how specific recommendations from the VERITY can be applied in real-life individual, institutional or policy contexts.

GOAL

The Scenario-Building Training aims to make VERITY's Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science more actionable and transformative, supporting their clarity, relevance and feasibility. It can also be used outside the VERITY project, as a flexible resource for exploring the practical implementation of recommendations in other contexts.

REQUIREMENTS

The Scenario-Building Training starts with reviewing the [VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science](#) and selecting one recommendation to work on. Users then describe the socio-political context and identify both enabling and hindering factors, while also mapping the key stakeholders who should be engaged. Next, they assess critical variables such as time, funding and resources before developing three possible scenarios: a feasible scenario that reflects what can realistically be achieved, a best-case scenario with the most positive outcomes, and a worst-case scenario that considers potential risks and setbacks. For each scenario, users outline concrete steps, risks and sustainability measures. Finally, the expected impacts are evaluated, and scenarios are refined iteratively, ideally in collaboration with a diverse group of stakeholders.

DURATION

Max. 4 hours (dependent on individual or group work).

PARTICIPANTS

Stewards of Trust, i.e. organisations, groups of individuals, who are responsible for guiding societal trust in science and facilitating science-society co-creation. Their responsibility stems either from their official mandate and mission, or from their *de facto* power and influence.

FOR WHOM IS THIS IMPORTANT?

The Scenario-Building Training can be used by all categories of Stewards of Trust (SOTs), such as policymakers, researchers, educators, funders, or science communicators, to create application scenarios. It can also be used outside the VERITY project, by anyone interested in exploring recommendation implementation approaches and methodological tools for scenario-building, as a flexible resource for exploring the practical implementation of recommendations in other contexts.

WHAT IS THIS ABOUT?

The Scenario-Building Training is a practical resource that guides stakeholders through structured exercises to test how the VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science can be applied in real-world settings. By creating application scenarios, users can identify opportunities, challenges, barriers and risks, and plan for feasible, best-case, and worst-case outcomes. It supports Stewards of Trust and other relevant stakeholders in translating recommendations into actionable strategies to foster trust in science, and it can also be applied in broader contexts.

WHY IS THIS IMPORTANT?

The Scenario-Building Training is important because it bridges the gap between recommendations and practice. It helps stakeholders move from abstract guidance to concrete implementation, ensuring that strategies to foster trust in science are realistic, adaptable, and sustainable. By anticipating risks and uncertainties, identifying enabling and hindering factors, and planning practical steps, the training supports users to turn ideas into action both within VERITY and in broader contexts.

Beyond its methodological value, the training also serves a wider purpose of fostering public trust in science. By guiding Stewards of Trust (SOTs) through the application of VERITY's recommendations, it supports systemic improvements in key areas such as building trustworthy science, strengthening education, engaging the public in research, building effective science communication, and developing supportive policy frameworks. It highlights the importance of collaboration across diverse actors in the ecosystem of trust, from policymakers and researchers to educators, communicators and funders, ensuring that scientific practices remain transparent, inclusive and responsive to societal needs.

PRACTICAL TIPS

The Scenario-Building Training can be carried out individually or in groups. However, it provides the most valuable insights into the practical application of a given recommendation when a group of interested stakeholders (minimum 2–5 people) from the same organisation, or working on the same trust-in-science issue, jointly reflect on the key enabling and hindering conditions at the macro (socio-political), meso (organisational), and micro (individual) levels. The maximum duration refers to the time

required for such a group to complete all steps and assess the most important underlying conditions across the three scenarios.

For individual work, we recommend first reflecting on the most feasible scenario. This may generate new ideas about the most relevant enabling factors for achieving better results, as well as the most serious risks and barriers that could prevent feasible implementation of the recommendation in your context. The final step is particularly important in individual work: your results should be reviewed by another person, preferably from a different professional or scientific background but with the same level of knowledge of the trust-in-science issue. If you still have doubts about certain steps of the Scenario-Building Training after reading the step-by-step guide below, we recommend consulting the seven examples developed during the VERITY Scenario-Building Workshop on 27 March 2025.

WHAT ARE THE NEXT STEPS?

STEP 1: Selection of a recommendation

Check the VERITY Protocol of Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science (available on the [VERITY website](#), [Embassy of Good Science](#) and Zenodo). Choose one recommendation that you want to implement in practice, e.g. in your daily work or in general in your organisation or projects. The main objective is to enhance **societal trust in science**, but you can decide on a more concrete application field related to your/your organisation's work where the recommendation would be beneficial. Check the provided examples for such application fields.

- Which of the recommendations (or elements of one recommendation) do you already apply in your professional or expert routine?
- Can you name a context and describe a typical scenario?
- How do you integrate the recommendation's objective in your daily activities to ensure an enhanced trust in science?

STEP 2: Set the problem context

Define the broader (socio-economic, political) and narrower (institutional) context of the problem to be solved. Consider all background issues that can have a direct or indirect influence on the successful implementation of the recommendation. List general assumptions that you can make about the recommendation, i.e. list all those educated premises that you consider as a starting point for an effective application scenario. These assumptions are the starting points on which further reasoning and development of the scenario can be built. These assumptions can vary in nature and might relate to specific contexts like economics or social interactions.

- What is the core problem that needs to be solved to foster trust in science? What are the basic assumptions on which the application scenario can be built on?
- What are the socio-economic, political, and cultural aspects that fundamentally shape the implementation of the recommendation?
- What are the main organisational or institutional settings that potentially affect the implementation of the recommendation?

STEP 3: Identify the relevant stakeholders

Identify the main individual or organisational stakeholders (Stewards of Trust) involved in the practical application of the recommendation. These stakeholders might include those who are affected by the main issue and those who can substantially contribute to the proposed solutions. Divide between game changers (or systematic innovators) and beneficiaries under the premise that roles can constantly change. In this framework, consider also the potential collaboration between various stakeholders (ecosystematic view).

- Who can benefit, can be affected negatively by or can impact the scenario related to the selected recommendation?
- Who is involved in the practical application of the recommendation within and beyond your organisation?
- How do you ensure that different voices, values and interests are engaged in the innovation/problem-solving process, including hard-to-reach or marginalised stakeholders?

STEP 4: Identify the key variables

Identify the key variables, i.e. those critical factors that can severely influence the implementation of the selected recommendation. Such factors can be divided to enabling and hindering factors, and might include time, money, human and other resources and capacities, equipment, goodwill of stakeholders, etc. These factors serve for defining suitable intervention points within your scenario. At this stage, no specific activities should be drawn up, but the general terms of the different scenarios should be constructed, i.e. key intervention points within and beyond the organisational setting with consideration of the role of identified relevant stakeholders.

- What are the enabling factors and strategies to facilitate the effective implementation of the recommendation?
- What are the hindering factors, i.e. obstacles and challenges that impede progress of a successful scenario-building?
- What are the key intervention points for the scenario?
- How can the identified stakeholders be involved in the innovation/problem-solving process?

STEP 5: Describe the main outputs of the most feasible scenario

Given the already determined elements, the outputs of a baseline scenario should be elaborated, i.e. the practical outputs to be achieved if the identified stakeholders work effectively together, by use of the identified intervention points, towards the joint achievement of the set objectives under the given circumstances. These tangible outputs can include concrete products, such as educational materials or communication events, but also cover less material accomplishments, such as increased information exchange or a mutual learning process.

The scenario-building methodology uses design thinking to develop fresh ideas and an out-of-the-box perspective: You can start to think of a worst-case or a best-case scenario to trigger your creativity and vision. Our instruction uses the most feasible scenario as a starting point, i.e. a realistic plan to achieve, considering the crucial key variables. This initial brainstorming on the most strategic options for a scenario supports further idea generation towards a best-case and worst-case scenario. The best-case should deliberately go beyond what is really under the current conditions and aim to define outputs that are to be achieved in the future when the present assumptions and underlying enabling factors favourably change. The worst-case should serve as a reminder what could happen, if no action is taken or the well-intended initiatives to enhance trust in science are not properly planned or encounter insurmountable structural or organisational barriers.

- **Most feasible scenario:** What are the outputs to be realistically achieved given the current enabling and hindering conditions?
- **Best-case scenario:** What are the results to be ultimately aimed for when all the circumstances are ideal to apply the recommendation?
- **Worst-case scenario:** What can happen in case, e.g. the recommendation is applied to an inadequate context, stakeholders are not well-informed or well-addressed, no action can be taken, or the implementation is inadequately planned?

STEP 6: Define the actionable steps leading towards achieving the objectives

Reverting from the main outputs identified, the actionable steps should be listed that are positively necessary for the successful implementation of the selected recommendation. The training envisages working with the most feasible scenario, but additional steps can be considered for the best-case scenario or even detrimental actions for the worst-case scenario. All action steps should consider the identified stakeholders to be involved, as well as the key intervention points towards which certain actions might lead. The action should include steps that mitigate expected and unforeseen risks, as well as capitalise on arising opportunities.

- What are the main actionable steps needed from you and each stakeholder to achieve the objectives defined for our scenario?
- How do you ensure that your implementation actions can adapt to unforeseen results or changes in the underlying conditions? (e.g. societal, economic, political)
- How do you ensure to capitalise on arising opportunities through your actions?

STEP 7: Describe the main outcomes of the most feasible scenario (impact)

Having planned the actionable steps resulting in the defined outputs, the main outcomes of the most feasible scenario should be detailed. Outcomes represent the longer-term effect and impact of the applied scenario on individuals, groups or the broader context. The changes occurring as a result of the identified outputs should first be reflected on, with the aim of specifying at least one outcome. The assessment of the outcome should include the understanding of the wider outreach, the potential transferability and significance of the scenario actions (impact aspect) and the duration of the consequences of such actions and key intervention points (long-term effect perspective).

- Build a vision and a mission: what is the main output and outcome of the successfully fulfilled feasible scenario?
- What are the main benefits? Who are the main beneficiaries of the impacts of your scenario?
- How can potentially negative impacts be transformed into assets or socially innovative outcomes?

STEP 8: Develop an appropriate impact measurement framework

As outcomes are less tangible than outputs and might involve less quantifiable patterns such as behavioural change, the appropriate identification/development of key performance indicators (KPIs) is crucial to track observable longer-term trends, such as an increase in skills or shifts in the behaviour of certain population segments, which is potentially caused by successful interventions of our implementation. Consider at least one key performance indicator (KPI) with which a durable outcome can be measured for later analysis.

- What are the KPIs with which to measure the long-term effects and impact of the applied scenario?
- Is the KPI strategically aligned with my organisation or project?
- Is the KPI operationally actionable within my organisation or project?
- How long will it take to reach your objective/s?
- How do you measure these KPIs in a conceivable way?
- Foresight: In which ways has the scenario application impacted your organisation or project?

STEP 9: Re-iteration of the scenario-building process

As certain implementation issues can be overlooked at the first attempt of the scenario-building exercise, it is recommended to repeat all the steps at least one more time, preferably with the involvement of other actors. The methodology can be reapplied at pre-defined regular intervals to establish an innovative process in your organisation or when new information comes to light. This follow-up can help to overcome any challenges or concerns arising towards the realisation of the determined objectives or to simply revise vital points of the scenario for better results.

- How do you promote reflection with the other participants on the most feasible scenario?
- How do you ensure that relevant new information concerning the recommendation or results is regularly provided to the participants of the scenario-building exercise?

VERITY SCENARIO-BUILDING WORKSHEET: STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE

<p>Objective to be Achieved</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p>
<p>Stakeholders/ Stewards of Trust</p> <p>Identify the main stakeholders or groups involved in the scenario: Who is mainly affected by the problem?</p> <p>Who can contribute to the solution?</p> <p><i>Divide between game changers (or systemic innovators) and beneficiaries under the premise that roles can change.</i></p>	<p>Describe the problem.</p> <p>Describe the context and the background of your scenario.</p> <p>Include any relevant information about the recommendation.</p> <p>List general assumptions that you can make about the recommendation and your scenario.</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <p>List critical factors that will influence and can change the scenario. These could include resources, constraints, needs or other factors.</p>	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p> <p>Describe the ideal outcome if everything goes as planned.</p>	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <p>Describe the potential challenges and negative outcomes.</p>	
<p>Most Feasible Scenario</p> <p>Describe the most realistic outcome considering current conditions.</p>	
<p>Impacts</p> <p>Describe major impacts of the most feasible scenario.</p>	<p>Actions</p> <p>Define the major steps for the implementation of your most feasible scenario.</p> <p>Include steps to mitigate risks.</p> <p>Include steps to capitalise on opportunities.</p>
<p>Metrics</p> <p>Identify the metrics to measure the success of the most feasible scenario. These could include key performance indicators (KPIs) and other relevant measurements.</p>	

VERITY SCENARIO-BUILDING WORKSHEET: EXAMPLES

EXAMPLE 1

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Distinguish trust in science from trust in decision-making supported by science</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: Phasing out fossil fuel transportation at the EU level</p>
<p>Stakeholders A dedicated task force focused on climate and fossil fuel transport transitions.</p> <p>Core members:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientists from multiple disciplines • Policymakers • Civil society representatives • Industry actors • Journalists and communicators • Academia and university deans • International and EU bodies 	<p>Context: There is a scientific consensus that action is needed. However, there is no societal consensus on how this should happen. The industry has influence and is integrated across sectors. Industry interests shape and influence proposed solutions.</p> <p>Core issue: There is scientific consensus that something needs to be done, but no single solution, and no societal consensus on the how.</p> <p>Assumption: Trust may be undermined if the task force's workings are not communicated clearly and transparently.</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timeframe: How much time is given to the task force to carry out their work? • EU regulatory requirements • Conflict of interest • Bridging science and policy • Transparent process • Feasibility and clarity of communication 	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p> <p>The task force follows a standardised and transparent procedure, which includes: (1) public consultations, (2) cross-disciplinary collaboration, (3) transparent communication about how and why decisions are made, (4) clear criteria for selection of task force members and decision-making, (5) active dissemination of recommendations in accessible formats for different communities and disciplines.</p>	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government imposes non-disclosure on the task force's activities. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal dissent: Task force members or scientists publicly criticise or attack one another, which leads to public confusion and erosion of trust. • Recommendations are delegitimised, and media narratives focus on conflict. 	
<p>Most Feasible Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The task force delivers quality work but is attacked by stakeholders who do not benefit from the policy outcomes. • These groups may mobilise distrust or attempt to undermine scientific credibility. • Scientists are blamed for decisions made by policymakers (mitigated by watchdogs and citizen councils). 	
<p>Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better public understanding of the difference between scientific evidence and policy decisions • Prevention of scapegoating scientists for unpopular or politically sensitive decisions • Shift public discourse towards accountability of policymakers, not just the science informing decisions 	<p>Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a standardised process for task forces • Increase of engagement with society, including underrepresented communities • Development of spaces for emotional or personal expressions from affected groups • Creation of independent watchdog bodies and citizen councils to observe and evaluate process integrity • Acknowledgement of those affected negatively by policies to reduce backlash
<p>Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce standardised trust-related questions in Eurobarometer surveys. • Track media and social media sentiment around science-based policy (soft perceptions). • Use citizen council input to collect both qualitative and quantitative data on public trust. 	

EXAMPLE 2

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Advocate for inclusive authorship policies in academic publishing to credit citizen contributions</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science policy makers (innovators) • Academic publishers (innovators) • Researchers and scientists (beneficiaries) • Citizen scientists (beneficiaries) <p>In this specific scenario, science communicators were not seen as important key stakeholders.</p>	<p>Problem: A research-performing organisation follows a mission-based inclusive authorship but not formalised steps and wants to change this.</p> <p>Context: The organisation wants to ensure that citizens contributing to research projects are recognised and rewarded appropriately in academic publications.</p> <p>The organisation’s culture and policies need changes to make this formalised and not based on personal connections.</p> <p>Assumption: There is a growing recognition of the value of citizen contributions to scientific research, meaning that academic publishers are open to revising authorship policies, and researchers are willing to acknowledge and credit citizen contributions.</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing organisational authorship policies and guidelines • Existing level of citizen involvement in research projects • Attitudes of researchers and publishers towards inclusive authorship • Impact on the credibility and integrity of academic publications 	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results are inclusive authorship policies re-adopted at the organisation, leading to increased recognition and motivation for citizen scientists. Which in return results in more collaborative and innovative research projects with the research-performing organisation. 	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance from researchers and administrators within the organisation leads to minimal or no changes in authorship policies. Citizen contributions remain formally unrecognised, causing frustration and disengagement among citizen scientists. 	
<p>Most Feasible Scenario</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gradual adoption of inclusive authorship policies fuelled by the support of management (might be first based on a positive example from a pioneer department or discipline). There is a positive shift in recognising citizen contributions, but full implementation takes time and sustainability questions linger. 	
<p>Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steady improvement in the recognition of citizen contributions Gradual increase in public engagement and trust in science 	<p>Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of inclusive authorship policies with willing researchers under the supervision of supporting management Organisation of participatory feedback loops to counter potential organisational resistance and identify potential weak points, also involving citizen opinions Implementation of a potential trial in one department or discipline to test the functioning of the new policies Codification of the new policies on inclusive authorship Development monitor systems and evaluate the implementation Sharing success stories and best practices to encourage wider adoption (in case of successful organisational or department-level adoption)
<p>Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of research projects within organisation crediting citizen contributions Level of satisfaction and engagement among citizen scientists and researchers Potential change in public perception and trust in scientific research 	

EXAMPLE 3

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Incorporate critical thinking, epistemic education (including philosophy of science and citizen science), and media literacy into primary, secondary, and higher education curricula</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: People’s mindset is not tuned to engage critically with information, in particular content on social media, due to underlying logical fallacies and biases.</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educators • Science communicators • Research institutions • Social media • Traditional news outlets • Industry actors 	<p>Context: Critical thinking skill is not taught adequately across all levels of education – formal learning is not prepared to deal with new challenges.</p> <p>Informal learning needs to be acknowledged as an area for development.</p> <p>Information is now increasingly sought from unreliable outlets, such as social media and influencers.</p> <p>Information consumers can be naïve and not capable of critical evaluation of reliable sources and data.</p> <p>The increasing use of AI-generated news and information might further reduce level of critical thinking.</p> <p>Assumption: Improving critical thinking about how, who, where, why information is generated will help people know what to trust and believe.</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The wider societal context should be taken into consideration when designing interventions such as education or training. • What are the proper incentives/motivating forces for people to start with trainings on critical thinking? • The fundamental change in the level of control over current curricula at primary and secondary school levels requires a sustained collaboration of diverse stakeholders (educators, communicators, researchers, policymakers) at national level. 	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p>	

- Critical thinking skills become a standard part of curricula at all levels of education and are given more visibility (rather than being covert).
- Curricula are aligned with fostering information-based decision making, taking into account societal and historical context.

Worst Case Scenario

- Politicians 'weaponise' (dis)information and the uncertainty of scientific evidence for their own ends.
- Social media outlets and influencers distort the traditional ways of information and news collection, further eroding critical reflection and fact-checking.
- The overreliance on AI (in scientific context) will further erode critical reflection (and trust in science).

Most Feasible Scenario

- Not an overall re-structuring of curricula but incremental systematic changes and practical trainings are implemented.
- Most feasible is start with early education and focus on the youngest generations growing up in the age of AI (discussion of AI could be a good jumping-on point for formal education and informal trainings).
- Some parts of society (but not all) are reached with the training or revised curricula.
- The development of an educational path on how to be 'prepared' for mis/disinformation/fake news is taken seriously by all relevant stakeholders (empowerment of teachers is needed to achieve this).

Impacts

- Progressively increased awareness of critical thinking in certain communities
- More people being able to respectfully engage in debates and hear each other's point of view

Actions

- Identify and acknowledge how each discipline can promote critical thinking
- Approach critical thinking as a methodology to incorporate to existing curricula
- Engage different people through interdisciplinary approaches, with a specific focus on hard-to-reach groups
- Training of teachers (empowerment) for critical thinking
- Explicit education/training on AI and open discussion on AI-generated materials/content

Metrics

- Number of curricula incorporating courses on critical thinking or use of AI (social media)

- Number of teachers (educators) prepared to teach critical thinking courses
- Number of school children being taught for critical thinking
- Number of events and other actions to cultivate critical thinking

EXAMPLE 4

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Encourage partnerships between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create science and align research with societal needs, ensuring transparency, accountability, and shared benefits.</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: Industry and academic stakeholders differ in research perspectives, objectives, needs, values – common understanding and cooperation is infrequent even though mutual benefits and interests exist.</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments • Universities • Citizens, including citizens representatives • Industry • Science communicators 	<p>Context: Partnerships can be based upon already existing best practices, such as projects leading to sustainable outcomes as 'spin-offs'.</p> <p>The government is responsible to creative incentives for both industry and academia to collaborate with each other, in particular if the two sides do not encourage cooperation themselves.</p> <p>Industry-academic partnership must be opened to quadruple helix actors and include considerations on the natural environment: without including citizens, societal needs of research cannot be validated.</p> <p>Assumption: industry and academic stakeholders aim to cooperate with each more frequently, but structural barriers hinder.</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding requirements are often not explicit enough to foster this cooperation. • Financial (and other) incentives: motivation why a cooperation is beneficial for both sides? • The willingness of industry and academia to cooperate with each other should be facilitated: both industry and academia may have arguments and tactics why they do not seek cooperation with each other. <p>Transparency on both sides: e.g. in commercialisation. Example: if an IP is planned after the cooperation has ended (e.g. the industry partner uses the IP of an open access publication from the university partner to apply it in the design of a new process or product), this intention should be declared from the very beginning.</p>	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supportive actors (decision-makers in academy and industry at middle or top level) systematically start common projects and other actions based on well-formulated common interests and benefits • The mutual learning process leads to an increased number of durable projects in more disciplines. 	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power imbalance and unilateral dependence. Example: the industry partner puts pressure on the academic partner not to publish specific data or results. • Non-transparent cooperation conducted in an untrusting environment for own reasons of both sides, while pretending to have mutual interests. 	
<p>Most Feasible Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding agencies develop such requirements that become an important leverage to promote partnerships between specific industry-academy actors. • Policymakers or CSOs incentivise industry-academy actors by showcasing the importance to promote societal goods, thus strengthening the focus of research on meeting what are actually the societal needs of our time. 	
<p>Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal needs better considered in research closer to markets. • Better commercialisation of research aligned with societal needs and values. • New or adapted forms of industry-academia cooperation, complemented with citizen engagement, leading to increased trust among stakeholders. 	<p>Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify mutual interests and goals. • Establish a project team able to learn from each other. • Define the collaboration framework and the involvement of citizens • Consider power imbalance and funding sources. • Monitor and evaluate the results for sustainability and upscale.
<p>Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative metrics: scientific output (publications), intellectual property (patents), leveraged funding, commercial outcome, investment into human resources (number of new jobs created), number of citizen engagement actions • Qualitative indicators: level of knowledge exchange, strategic alignment of industry-academy goals, societal impact, sustainable adapted or new forms of collaboration 	

EXAMPLE 5

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Identify the diverse characteristics and needs of different communities through consultative social scientific methods, such as interviews and focus groups, which will provide insights for designing and implementing tailored strategies for public engagement.</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: Citizens are not involved enough in R&I governance consultations, at the same time consultation fatigue must be faced.</p> <p>Context: Citizens are infrequently consulted about their needs and perspectives in scientific issues and if yes, outcomes are rarely used, which contributes to frustration.</p> <p>Participatory processes often end with the consultation; no further engagement follows.</p> <p>Engagement with remote communities is still challenging despite digital means and media.</p> <p>Assumption: Pivotal initiatives need more time and resources – often funded activities stop too early after building communities and establishing ways of communication.</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science-society facilitators • Public engagement professionals • Different community members such as community centres, neighbourhood associations; local champions and change-makers with a high motivation to contribute or stir processes (these are often the most outspoken in the community) • Citizens, including civil society representatives • Researchers 	
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional facilitators are needed to supervise such processes. • Ways to bring in local knowledge need to be defined to enable an appropriate knowledge transfer between different types of experts and citizens. • Regarding the outreach strategy, the expectation management and a clear presentation of objectives. <p>Consultation fatigue can become a challenge during consultation processes.</p>	
<p>Best Case scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the UK context, a Community Interest Company (CIC) is a social enterprise designed to benefit the community. It is a municipal organisation with a mission to promote various scientific issues, e.g. educational activities and lay a focus on inclusivity through various events and projects, particularly for underrepresented and socio-economically disadvantaged families • This concept can be upscaled and adapted to further bottom-up needs. • To overcome a consultation fatigue, CICs also implements reverse consultations. 	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-size-fits-all public engagement processes (without proper needs assessment) will lead to non-participation of citizens and a decreased 	

motivation of researchers and other related stakeholders, leading to a vicious cycle of fewer consultations based on unsatisfying results (cited by unsupportive policymakers and government bodies).

Most Feasible Scenario

- In a less organised way than CICs, public engagement is undertaken by engaged science-society facilitators and public engagement professionals.
- An inclusivity plan is developed and carried out flexibly, e.g. adapting to challenges during the outreach to marginalised communities and providing enough resources to create benefits.
- Funding such as human and other resources are available for a participatory process lasting beyond the public consultation.
- Lessons learnt are used to plan and design tailor-made strategies for the public engagement of associated or other communities.

Impacts

- Creating new exchange channels between local communities and research and innovation.
- Strengthening trust in science and active citizenship.

Actions

- Capacity building will be provided for actors responsible for public engagement, including legal aspects and policymaking.
- Mechanism should be developed to include all voices and to update on objectives and activities in a transparent manner.
- Trustworthy relations should be established between researchers, facilitators and community members or citizens.

Metrics

- The first metric highlighted is the number of community-led research projects implemented (post assessment).
- The second is the official adoption of the VERITY Protocol of Recommendations in projects at the intersection of science-society and the influence of these projects on the general adaption of existing public guidelines and frameworks (regional, national, European).
- Another suggestion includes the long-term studies on how many young people engaged in STEM activities opt-in STEM careers.

EXAMPLE 6

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Develop proactive strategies leveraging trusted messengers to counteract misinformation and conspiracy theories</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: Local communities are hard to reach in terms of controversial scientific questions affecting their lives.</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science communicators • Researchers • Gatekeepers or trusted 'messengers' (people who know their community and give credit to scientists) • Local citizens (everybody who did not express a negative view, including previously uninterested/uncommitted people) 	<p>Context: Citizens usually tend to have low scientific literacy and understanding, leading to situations when 'louder' stakeholders with seemingly convincing arguments can turn ordinary citizens towards anti-scientific or pseudo-scientific views.</p> <p>Citizens need to be reached by 'trusted messengers' transmitting reliable scientific news relevant for their daily lives.</p> <p>Gatekeepers are also crucial to connect messengers/science communicators with local communities.</p> <p>Assumption: Platforms for (scientific) debates exist and people should be reached at local level (through communities) preferably by researchers (who tend to be the best science ambassadors).</p>
<p>Key Variables (Touchpoints)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextualisation of science communication at a local setting: researchers should be presented also as part of the community and citizens who are relatable (i.e. talk with passion about their research but can also relate to people's everyday issues). • A multidisciplinary approach was considered to be the best approach since most likely complex scientific issues necessitate it. Potentially science must be re-defined for the local environment: What does science really mean to people? • Timeframe (how much time do we have to achieve the goals?): scientists should have time to engage with the public and local communities should be given a necessary amount of time ("patience") to 'digest' the scientific information. • Funding – potential local, regional or national sources. 	
<p>Best Case Scenario</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The multidisciplinary approach works, and different scientists are truly engaged with the local community in scientific discussion with the support of gatekeepers in a long-term sustainable process that results in fostering trust in science. 	
<p>Worst Case Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The gatekeepers are not reached within a local community and therefore, science remains in 'labs' and in turn its results do not reach the people whose lives might be significantly affected by the given scientific issue. 	
<p>Most Feasible Scenario</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participatory action research happens where scientists from some fields (but not from all fields leading to a limited multidisciplinary approach) are in touch with some segments of the local community building towards a mutual understanding of the scientific issue at hand. Some people take up interest and actively communicate with researchers while others stay uninterested or even hostile, making the science engagement efforts' long-lasting impact (sustainability) questionable for a longer time. The communication objectives focus on showcasing the tangible benefits of science to the local community (not withholding the fact that science is fallible) and to make people better understand what scientific results are relevant for their daily lives. Social media might be used for science communication and community engagement in certain situations (depending on local settings and scientific fields). 	
<p>Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interest is raised in science and potentially trust is raised by motivated reasoning instead of 'blind' faith in science. People better understand the wide fields of possibilities in science. 	<p>Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The scientific issue at hand and the local context (community) should identified. Scientists with interest in science communication should be identified and get proper training in science communication. Scientists from multiple fields should be connected with local community gatekeepers. Gatekeepers and scientists should get acquainted with each other and formulate the best ways to connect with local people. An implementation plan with impact assessment should be developed and followed upon.
<p>Metrics</p>	

- Lead measures should include quantifiable metrics such as no. of events (forums/townhall meetings) organised with local community members or a number of stakeholders attending such events.
- Lag measures should include metrics measuring behavioural and opinion changes within the local community, e.g. longitudinal surveys with simple ranked order questions before and after the 'intervention'.

EXAMPLE 7

<p>Objective to be Achieved: Adapt the ethical oversight mechanisms to the changing research environment, including inter-disciplinary, international, and multi-sector research.</p>	<p>Problem/Context/Assumptions</p> <p>Problem: Existing ethics policies do not have clear monitoring tools, only general guidance.</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration • Funding bodies • Universities • Researchers • Journalists/Publishers (General and Science) • Research ethic bodies • NGOs/Activist Groups 	<p>Context: There is a variety of national, local, institutional, disciplinary context to consider: there is a deregulation pressure in some cases, coupled with defunding and lack of human resources.</p> <p>There is a generally re-active nature of policies as regards the new challenges posed by AI.</p> <p>The raise of Open Access practices helps better consider ethics in research practices.</p> <p>Wrong incentives are counterproductive: the motto “publish or perish” can lead to fraudulent/misleading practices.</p> <p>Media attacks against specific scientific areas (climate change, bioethics) can be distorting.</p> <p>Assumption: Many scientists and policymakers do not fully grasp the impact of ethics; therefore, ethical oversight mechanisms are often only formalistically applied.</p>
<p>Key Variables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There should be a political will to bring policymakers to the same table as scientists (intersectoral forum for exchanges). • There should be a critical reflection on what functioned until now and what could be the new ethics challenges. • Clear and consistent ethics regulations should also include an appropriate monitoring framework in the future. • Adapted over/foresight mechanisms should be anticipatory for new ethics challenges. • High-quality training on ethics and integrity is needed for different stakeholders, e.g. scientists, policymakers, funding bodies. • Public outreach and awareness-raising or advocacy activities should be accepted as instruments and supported by policymakers. 	

Best Case scenario

- Policies at all levels have strong ethical dimensions with clear indicators for implementation.
- Permanent collaborative bodies ensure that policymakers, scientists and other stakeholders continuously work on improving the regulatory frameworks.
- Trained and competent professionals share their knowledge about applied ethics.
- Clear linkages are established between ethics, Open Access and FAIR principles (including transparency, reproducibility, and responsible reuse).

Worst Case Scenario

- Ethical oversight mechanisms remain performative (mentioning the use of ethics but not really being concrete on the how) or follow the 'principlism' approach (the use of ethical principles remain too abstract, contributing to a 'checklist' approach).

Most Feasible Scenario

- The 'carrot and stick' approach prevails: top-down requirements are imposed by funders, scientists and ethic boards to foster bottom-up consultations and education aiming to achieve a new ethical oversight mechanism.
- Ethics advisors and advisory boards are being taken more seriously (also because of funding requirements) as integral part of the scientific knowledge production
- More institutions move towards a mandatory establishment of structures and processes for research ethics with the following minimum requirements: accountability, transparency, openness, inclusiveness, roles and duties, compliance, monitoring powers, enforcement powers, intersection with technologies and AI supervisory bodies.

Impacts

- Raised awareness about ethics
- Increased protective measures, e.g. whistleblowers
- Change in dynamics of academia and pressure on stakeholders
- Impact on vulnerable groups in research: risks, safeguards and mitigating measures to be planned

Actions

- Analyse the incentive structures in academia.
- Identify best practices and synergies across initiatives.
- Establish permanent bodies and conduct international workshops for knowledge exchange, awareness-raising and development of new ethics oversight mechanisms.
- Advocate for a public ethics body in EU/CoE.
- Lobby EC to include research ethics in Whistleblowing Directive.

Metrics

- Development of an ethics dashboard with designated indicators (analogous to rule of law indicators monitored worldwide).
- Universal ethics checklist with indicators such as retractions or editorial actions per person/institution, hours of ethics training per project/researcher/participant and the number of institutional initiatives (projects) integrating ethics in science.

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